

Quriyozov Elmurod Rajabboy o‘g‘li

Digital technologies in the system of public finance and public procurement – risks and opportunities

Tashkent State University of Economy,
a master’s student of MSc-Finance,
Muminova Dildora Mumin qizi,
muminovadildora571@gmail.com
tel.: +998903367445

The Ministry of Economy and Finance,
the Department of ensuring openness of
public procurement and information-
analysis, a senior specialist,
Urolov Bekhruz Uljaevich,
ruz_bex@mail.ru , tel.: +998973669977

Tashkent State University of Economy,
Associate Professor of the Department of
“Finance and Financial Technologies”,
Supervisor: Tursunkhodjaeva Shirin,
sh.tursunkhodjaeva@tsue.uz
tel.: +998933973737

Abstract: The integration of digital technologies into public finance and procurement systems offers transformative potential for enhancing transparency, efficiency, and accountability in government operations. This article explores the opportunities and risks associated with the adoption of digital tools in the Republic of Uzbekistan —such as artificial intelligence (AI), and big data analytics—in the public finance and procurement sector. Key opportunities include *streamlined financial management, reduced transaction costs, improved data accuracy, and enhanced fraud detection capabilities*. However, the transition to digital systems also presents significant challenges and risks, including cybersecurity risks, potential data privacy concerns, and the need for substantial investment in infrastructure and skills development. Furthermore, rapid digitalization can create regulatory and ethical dilemmas related to automated decision-making and algorithmic transparency. Through an examination of case studies and emerging trends, this article provides insights into best practices for mitigating risks while maximizing the

benefits of digital transformation in public finance and procurement. The findings aim to inform policymakers, technologists, and public finance professionals on building resilient, secure, and effective digital public finance systems.

Key words: *digital technologies, public finance, public procurement, risks, management.*

Digital transformation in public finance and public procurement has been a priority in Uzbekistan as part of broader reforms aimed at modernizing the country's economy, enhancing transparency, and improving efficiency in public administration. This shift to digital is part of the government's ongoing efforts to make financial management and procurement processes more accessible, reliable, and transparent. Currently, large-scale reforms in the field of public finance are implemented in the country. The public procurement system is among these significant areas. Public procurement is not only an instrument of economic regulation, but also an important factor in developing a business, attracting investment, ensuring transparency in the use of budget funds as well as eradicating corruption. [1]

In Uzbekistan's reforms - UZBEKISTAN DIGITAL INCLUSION PROJECT (P179108) on November 2, 2023. "The Uzbekistan Digital Inclusion Project is the first operation to support the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan in line with the "Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy" and "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". The priority for the Project is the creation of new digital jobs in the ITES segments, particularly targeting regional areas, and including digital job creation for youth, including women and persons with disabilities. The Project would contribute to the larger goal of building greater economic opportunities, creating more and better jobs, and facilitating private sector-led economic growth as indicated in the NDS (National Development Strategy). The Project will include gender-disaggregated indicators in the Results Framework with a target of 50 percent of the project beneficiaries being women.

The Project is articulated around three main areas for intervention: policy, infrastructure, and skills. These components seek to (i) enhance the enabling legal, regulatory, and institutional environment for a vibrant and inclusive ITES industry and for the broader digital economy; (ii) develop digital and language skills among youth, women, and other vulnerable groups necessary for employment in digitally enabled service sectors (iii) expand infrastructure for ITES industry in the regions of Uzbekistan; and (iv) support mechanisms for promoting Uzbekistan as an outsourcing destination.

The Project aims to create new digital jobs, improving the employability of its beneficiaries, help generate economic benefits from increasing their employment rates and placing them in jobs with higher earnings. Academic research shows that

people who acquire digital skills experience an increase in annual earnings of between 3-10 percent. [2]

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 5, 2019 No.4544 “On measures to further improve the public procurement system and the wide involvement of business entities in the public procurement process” starting from April 2020, electronic procedures for the implementation of tender and competitive bidding in the field of public procurement has been introduced in order to ensure the targeted spending of state customers funds and increase their efficiency, attract business entities by introducing new digital technologies in public procurement. In order to timely implement the Presidential Decree, introduce information and communication technologies in the field of public procurement, increase the level of competition among electronic public procurement operators, a new information system for an electronic tender (competition) for budget and corporate procurement has been developed.

According to the legislation of the republic, the system ensures the holding of competitions and tenders using the score method and the lowest price method. Customers are given the opportunity to independently select one of the two recognized assessment methods in the world, determine the criteria by which the proposals of the applicants will be evaluated, the relative values of the criteria (each of which can give a different score, depending on the importance of a particular indicator for customers). Criteria based on quantitative indicators (number of specialists, work experience in the market, price, delivery time, etc.) will be evaluated by the system independently, exclusively in an automatic mode, without involving human resources. Qualitative (expert) criteria is evaluated by members of the tender commission, who can work remotely in an online mode. Particular attention in the development of the system is paid to ensuring transparency and competition in tenders, combating corruption, conflicts of interest and other offenses.

The introduction of the electronic competition and tender system will improve our indicators as regard to creating favorable conditions for doing business (Doing Business) and fulfill the recommendations of the OECD international organization within the framework of the Istanbul Anti-Corruption Action Plan. Currently, the Ministry of Finance is developing a schedule for the gradual transition of tender and competitive bidding of all budget and corporate customers into digital form. The Ministry of Economy and Finance is closely cooperating in the implementation of electronic forms of tendering and public procurement with the joint venture XT - XARID TEXNOLOGIYALARI and the Uzbek Commodity Exchange, as well as in studying foreign experience and further improving electronic procurement with the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development. [3]

On the other hand, however, we may face challenges and risks as well. While significant progress has been made, our government is still facing challenges, including infrastructure gaps, cybersecurity risks, and the need for digital literacy training among public sector employees.

The effectiveness of fiscal policy—the collection and use of resources to stabilize the economic cycle, pursue distributional objectives, and enable public spending—depends crucially on the information and technologies available to government, and how it exploits them. Governments stimulate the economy during recessions and retrench during booms. They tax in order to finance social safety nets, health and education services, infrastructure, and so on. The design and implementation of fiscal policy is therefore fundamentally shaped by the reliability, timeliness, and detail of the information available to the government about the economy and its actors. [4] Deep-learning technologies are pushing the boundaries of digitalization one step further, with artificial intelligence machines now able to learn by themselves based on information fed to them. Using such technology, computers are now capable of designing industrial objects, generating scientific hypotheses, and even composing music ([McAfee and Brynjolfsson 2017](#)). [5] Digitalization has also vastly increased the possibilities for data collection and storage. In 2000 only 25 percent of data were stored digitally; by 2007 this metric had risen to 94 percent ([Ross 2016](#)). [6]

Technologies give a huge amount of opportunities. For example, through digitalization, government can potentially conduct current fiscal policy more effectively—doing what we do now, but better—and perhaps before too long, design policy in new ways—doing things, that is, that we do not, and cannot, do now. They can have better information, build better systems, and design and implement better policies. Of the digital revolutions many potential benefits, the most visible and crucial may well be the ability to collect, process, and disseminate more timely, easily accessible, and transparent information on economic activity. Greater storage capacity and computing power means that governments can now collect more information, by tracking and recording a vast range and volume of transactions and interactions.

IT solutions for different PFM functions are often siloed from each other, as well as from other government IT systems. While governments have become much better at producing financial information, they are still not very good at understanding whether their fiscal policies are having their intended impact. A big reason for this is that IT solutions are siloed in different government functions and departments, often using unharmonized data structures. *The way governments fund digital transformation incentivizes a solution-driven approach to PFM reform.* Too often governments try to deliver digital infrastructure in the same way they deliver

physical infrastructure. They attempt to specify all their requirements up front in a business case, contract suppliers to deliver the IT system, and budget only for the up-front capital cost. This process can take so long (an average of 8 years for a financial management information system) that the requirements have changed by the time the system is eventually implemented. More often, the project encounters internal resistance, because those specifying the requirements have not consulted well enough with the actual users of the system. [7]

Figure 1. What to make of the role of user needs? [8]

What needs to change to bring public finance into the digital era? *For all these reasons, we recommend three big shifts in thinking.* In isolation none of these are new recommendations, but together they constitute an emerging paradigm – *digital PFM*. A finance ministry adopting these shifts in mindset could generate important spillovers for the kind of [whole of government approach](#) to digital transformation towards which many governments now aspire.

- A funding and delivery model for sustainability. *Funding and delivering digital infrastructure are different from funding and delivering physical infrastructure.*

- The PFM system as part of a wider ecosystem of data, platforms, and services. *The capability to effectively exchange data and information across and between layers of government – often referred to as interoperability – requires a silo-busting mentality.* [New models](#) for thinking about the role of government in the digital era emphasize a reorganization of government around data, platforms, and services. This means shifting to a much more open architecture based on standardized open [application programming interfaces \(APIs\)](#).

- A flexible and responsive PFM system. *Like the IT systems that underpin them, PFM processes require ongoing iterative redesign to provide a system that is*

flexible to the ever-evolving needs of users and responsive to the problems policy makers are trying to solve.

Capabilities to solve problems will be necessary to deliver on policy promises like universal health coverage and respond to emerging crises around climate change and inequality. This means recognizing PFM and digital transformation as *means to an end* and bringing them together in a problem-driven approach to PFM reform.

Figure 2. Making ‘government-as-a-platform’ real [9] ([Source](#))

The Ministry of Economy and finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan has received financing from the World Bank toward the cost of the Institutional Capacity Building Project and intends to apply part of the proceeds for consulting services for the Ministry of Economy and finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Within the framework of the Decree UP No. – 6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the directions of “Digital Uzbekistan-2030” and measures for its effective implementation” dated October 5, 2020, the directions “Development of digital technologies in the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024-2026” provides for the widespread introduction of digital technologies into economic management and public finance systems, including strategic goals, priority areas, as well as medium- and long-term objectives for the development of the digital economy and e-government of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and also serves as the basis

for the wider introduction of digital technologies, including in the field of further improvement of mechanisms for providing electronic government services.

Project Background and Objectives

On May 24, 2019, the World Bank and Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan (MEF) agreed on a World Bank loan program called “Institutional Capacity Building Project” (ICBP) for Uzbekistan. The development objectives of ICBP are to strengthen public financial management (PFM) and enable the market operation of the corporate sector. This project has four components. 1) The first component, Improving PFM, aims to support improvements in areas fundamental to a functional PFM system that promotes the achievement of public policy objectives, improved performance, and institutionalized accountability. 2) The second component, Improving Conditions for Market Operation of the Corporate Sector, aims to support the restructuring and rightsizing of the State-Owned Enterprise (SOE) sector in Uzbekistan. 3) The third component, Improving Support Mechanisms for Reforms, aims to provide support to the newly established Economic Council, key regulatory agencies, and other public sector agencies expected to be identified as critical for implementing market reforms during project implementation. 4) The fourth component, Project Management, aims to provide support to the overall implementation arrangements for the project.

Within the framework of the Decree UP No. – 6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the directions of “Digital Uzbekistan-2030” and measures for its effective implementation” dated October 5, 2020, the directions “Development of digital technologies in the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024-2026” provides for the widespread introduction of digital technologies into economic management and public finance systems, including strategic goals, priority areas, as well as medium- and long-term objectives for the development of the digital economy and e-government of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and also serves as the basis for the wider introduction of digital technologies, including in the field of further improvement of mechanisms for providing electronic government services.

The main tasks for development of digital technologies of the Ministry are the following:

- implementing priority projects aimed at digitalization of the economy and public financial management system;
- developing the Ministry’s IT infrastructure and widespread introduction of modern digital technologies;
- ensuring information security of the Ministry's system;
- developing proposals to accelerate work on digitalization and implementation of digital technologies in the industry.

Consequently, when carrying out the above tasks, the Ministry shall seek advice from a reputable and qualified expert, including assistance to the Ministry in terms of digitalization. The expert is expected to provide international experience and practical activities in the field of IT. [10]

Here, we would like to draw your attention to some actual and important dilemmas which are, nowadays, encountered by those who are in charge of executing public procurement procedures in practice. Firstly, the account of public purchases made by corporate customers is not kept in an *aggregated manner*. Secondly, contracts concluded directly by state customers are currently concluded in *paper version* and *scanned version* are placed in the electronic system of public procurement – no electronically-generated templates. Thirdly, during the selection of the best offers made by state customers and the implementation of tenders, the procurement commission of the state customer check the absence of tax liabilities in the evaluation of the offers of the performers, and the absence of the single register of ‘dishonest performers’ through *separate programs* – there has not been developed a unique integrated checking system or a platform so far.

Meanwhile, we also would like to offer some solutions to these problems. For example, firstly, including the accounts of corporate customers into the treasury execution of the State budget. Secondly, electronic conclusion of direct contracts with government customers using the competitive method of public procurement. Thirdly, introduction of automatic verification by integrating the information about debtors of the executors and the information about the non-existence of the single register of dishonest executors with the relevant programs. [11]

The Government of Uzbekistan has outlined a vision for further advancements, including full integration of AI and machine learning into public finance and procurement systems, continued improvements in cybersecurity, and expanded digital literacy programs for both citizens and government employees.

In summary, Uzbekistan’s initiatives in digitizing public finance and procurement demonstrate a commitment to transparency, efficiency, and accountability. Through the sustained implementation of digital tools, Uzbekistan is paving the way for a modern, responsive public administration system.

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